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Approaches For The Physical Sorting Of Soft And Hard Magnetic Material Mixtures In The Context Of Rare Earth Recycling

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Abstract

Rare earth (RE) elements applied for magnets are considered as critical raw materials by most industrial countries. On the one hand, especially neodymium-iron-boron (NdFeB) magnets are essential for the current economic transformation as they are used for core technologies such as electric mobility and wind power causing continuously increasing demand. On the other hand, there is a significant supply chain risk due to poor market diversification and bad substitutability. This leads to various economic problems such as steadily rising prices, price volatility, and potential shortages. In addition, the primary production has a poor ecological footprint.

In this context, the recycling of NdFeB magnets has a high economic, geopolitical, and ecological potential. However, hardly any recycling is currently carried out on an industrial scale due to technical and organizational difficulties. As magnetic extraction from end-of-life (EOL) products by dismantling is only economically feasible in specific cases, the implementation of a universally applicable process based on shredding and multi-stage sorting is essential. Intensive research is currently being carried out for the further processing of the pure NdFeB granulate, but there is a lack of reliable separation processes for the hard and soft magnetic components of the ferrous shredding fraction, which are similar in terms of many physical properties. Therefore, the present paper discusses approaches based on physical sorting principles to close the existing gap in the overall process chain. The solution preferred by the authors is based on a multi-stage process chain realized as a flow process, which primarily exploits differences with regard to mechanical and magnetic characteristics.

Keywords

Rare Earth Magnets; Critical Raw Materials; Recycling; Physical Sorting; Hard And Soft Magnetic Materials

1. Introduction

As part of the Paris Agreement, nearly all countries agreed on the goal of limiting global warming to less than two degrees Celsius compared to the pre-industrial age, with a commitment to additional efforts to keep a 1.5 °C limit [1]. As a result, many states defined specific goals for carbon neutrality. For example, the “European Green Deal” by the European Union (EU) is aiming for a complete elimination of the net emissions of greenhouse gases until 2050 and is defining concrete measures [2]. Also, other major emitters such as the United States of America (USA) and the People's Republic of China (PRC) have set individual target dates and are increasing their efforts for climate protection [3, 4]. As a result, the global relevance of green technologies such as electric mobility and wind power is steadily increasing. This development is

leading to a sharp growth in demand for rare earth (RE) magnets, which are primarily used for highly efficient and power-dense motors and generators as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Forecasted demand for relevant green technologies and correlating impact on global demand for RE magnets (data source: [5–7])

In industrial practice, primarily sintered neodymium-iron-boron magnets (NdFeB) are used, which provide superior properties regarding coercivity and maximum energy product [8, 9]. NdFeB magnets consist of approx. one third light rare earth elements (LREE) such as neodymium (Nd) and praseodymium (PR) and a smaller proportion of heavy rare earth elements (HREE) such as dysprosium (Dy), terbium (Tb), gadolinium (Gd) and holmium (Ho). HREE are essential for high-performance applications as they serve to improve the coercivity and operating temperature range but in parallel have a significant price impact despite their small proportion. [10–14]

The market for NdFeB magnets and the related rare earth elements (REE) is characterized by the dominance of the PR of China for the entire value chain from ore mining and refining to the production of high-performance magnets [13–18]. There is also a risk that future demand could exceed supply from primary production despite increases in productivity [12, 13]. The combination of low market diversification, poor substitutability, and relevance for key technologies is a burden on the economy and jeopardizes the industrial strategy of industrial nations such as Germany, the United States, and Japan. For this reason, both the EU and the USA have declared relevant LREE and HREE to be critical raw materials of the highest category and are planning concrete measures to secure supply [19–22]. Another issue is the poor ecological footprint of primary production with radioactive contaminations, high greenhouse gas emissions, and chemical consumption [23–28].

In this context, the recycling of RE magnets from end-of-life (EOL) products can contribute to a secure and more sustainable supply with stabilized market prices. However, the necessary technical and organizational requirements are often lacking at present, with the result that currently almost no systematic recovery is carried out in western industry nations. The European recycling rate is currently below one percent. [14, 19, 24, 29–32] Consequently, there is a great need to develop and establish appropriate processes to be competitive and to meet the targets defined by political regulations. For example, the European “Critical Raw Materials Act” is calling for 25% of European demand to be covered by recycling by 2030 [22].

2. Potential process chains for the recovery of NdFeB magnets from shredded EOL products

Numerous alternative process routes are currently being developed that allow the recovery of rare earths from EOL magnets. Various pyro-, hydro- and electrometallurgical approaches are available for this purpose

[10, 14, 28, 33–36]. In contrast, the extraction of magnets from EOL products, which is essential for effective recycling, is currently somewhat neglected. For specific applications, it is expedient to dismantle the magnets from EOL products, which can then either be reused directly or recycled. However, certain requirements must be met for this approach. These include a significant content of RE magnets, the specific size and composition of the used magnets, sufficient demountability, high product volumes, and manageable product variance. [37, 38] In addition, the individual service life of EOL products must also be taken into account when choosing a recycling approach. In this context, design for recycling approaches and the labeling of rare earth content can make a contribution, but these approaches are currently only rudimentary at best. In industrial practice, specific product characteristics, the individual condition of EOL products, and lack of information additionally complicate dismantling approaches. It can therefore be assumed that dismantling can only compete economically with primary production in specific cases. Possible examples include hard disk drives and automotive traction motors, for which corresponding approaches with an increased degree of automation already exist. [33, 39–43] Another use case comprises very large magnets applied in wind turbines, magnetic resonance imaging scanners, or large motors and generators, so that a high manual effort is worthwhile [10, 14]. As an alternative hydrogen processing can be applied, which can be used universally. However, this process route has limitations regarding large-scale production due to the long process times and complex system technology. [44–47]

Accordingly, the implementation of a universally applicable process based on the existing process chain for EOL products is essential for the industrial recovery of rare earths on a large scale. Currently, the majority of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE), and electric motors in particular, are processed by shredding [47–49]. The material generated in this way is then sorted into fractions that are fed into raw material production. Standard processes include density sorting, magnetic separation, and eddy current separation. The most relevant resulting material groups include copper, aluminum, plastics, and the ferrous fraction, with copper normally being the main source of value in the recycling of electrical machines. The ferrous fraction, which is separated by magnetic separation, contains the majority of the magnets, as the established sorting process chain used does not differentiate between soft and hard magnetic components. Accordingly, the RE magnets contained in the material flow are melted down together with the steel scrap, whereby recovery of the REE from the slag is currently not economically feasible [33, 47]. As a result, there is a need for the integration of a sorting process into the already industrialized process chain that allows the separation of the hard magnetic fraction and the subsequent segregation of the RE magnets. The NdFeB recyclate obtained in this way can then be processed by hydro- or pyrometallurgy and the resulting REE can be fed back into the production process for new magnets. The following Figure 2 visualizes a potential overall process flow from the EOL product to the new magnet.

Figure 2: Potential process flow for the recovery of RE magnets from WEEE

This process to be developed closes a gap in the currently available process chain for WEEE but is complicated by various factors. The concentration of RE magnets in the material flow is very low, meaning that a very high material throughput is required for sufficient efficiency. Bandara et. al. determined an Nd content of 130 – 290 ppm in the ferrous fraction of shredded WEEE and other EOL products [50]. Other studies have found a slightly higher concentration of approx. 490 ppm [51]. In addition, the composition of the material flow varies greatly depending on the input material [46]. Furthermore, agglomerations occur as a result of the magnetic reaction forces or the fragmented magnets adhere to larger ferromagnetic objects in the material flow. Finally, RE magnets have many similar physical properties to relevant soft magnetic materials as shown in Table 1, which makes separation difficult.

Table 1: Physical properties of relevant soft and hard magnetic materials which can be found in the ferrous fraction of shredded electric machines [8, 52]

	Electrical & other steels	NdFeB	Hard ferrites	SmCo	AlNiCo
Source	Laminated core, housing, structural parts, etc.	Mainly rotors (high performance applications)	Mainly rotors (cost efficient applications)	Mainly rotors (high temperature applications)	Special applications (no relevance for motors)
Density (g/cm ³)	7.65	7.40 – 7.80	4.80 – 5.10	8.20 – 8.50	6.80 – 7.30
Curie temperature (°C)	745	310 – 380	450	720 – 820	700 – 860
Relative permeability	4000	1.04 – 1.12	1.05 – 1.20	1.04 – 1.12	1.30 – 6.20
Electrical resistivity (Ωm)	5.0 · 10 ⁻⁶	1.2 · 10 ⁻⁶	10 ⁻² –10 ²	5.0 · 10 ⁻⁷	5.0 · 10 ⁻⁷

3. Analysis of input material and approach for the physical sorting of shredded material

Schubert defines sorting in the context of process engineering as the sorting of macroscopic solid particles by utilizing the different physical properties of the materials [53]. Consequently, when developing a concept for a sorting process, the input material stream and the relevant physical properties of the involved materials must be systematically analyzed. In the present case, the input material comprises the ferrous fraction, which is separated by magnet sorting, meaning that only soft magnetic materials and technically relevant hard magnetic materials are included here. Due to the structure of electrical machines and other relevant EOL products, steel is the dominant component of the ferrous fraction, originating in particular from the laminated cores of stator and rotor (electrical steel) as well as from structural and housing parts. The permanent magnets (PM), on the other hand, only make up a small proportion. The focus of development is therefore on the separation of NdFeB from the steel components of the material stream, whereby the process should be realized as a continuous flow process in order to ensure sufficient throughput. A potential generic overall process chain is visualized in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Potential overall process chain for recovery of NdFeB from shredded EOL products

The use of NdFeB magnets dominates for electric motors, although hard ferrites also have a high economic relevance with a market share of approx. one third [18]. In this context, a complicating factor is the sometimes parallel use of NdFeB magnets and hard ferrites for the same products, which applies e. g. for compressors, pumps, and industrial motors. The RE magnet type samarium-cobalt (SmCo) is only used in special high-temperature applications, as the other magnetic properties are inferior and the costs higher compared to NdFeB. Also, aluminum-nickel-cobalt (AlNiCo) magnets can be neglected, as they are not used for electric motors due to their low coercivity. [50, 54] Accordingly, the establishment of dedicated sorting steps is negligible for these two material groups.

To increase the efficiency of the sorting process, it is essential to feed the process only with EOL products which could contain RE magnets, e. g. when recycling electric motors non-PM motors such as induction machines should be sorted out. In the future, a legal obligation to mark RE content and quantity could make a significant contribution [46, 55]. As long as there is no labeling standard, a distinction can often be made based on the application, the product type, or external product features. The pre-sorting can be realized either visually by human workforce or automatically by sensor systems. In both cases, the establishment of product databases is essential. If possible, also products containing hard ferrites should be sorted out as much as possible. The significantly lower energy product of hard ferrites compared to RE magnets is often compensated by a larger magnet volume, so that in rare cases conclusions can be drawn about the magnet type based on the magnet geometry. The following illustration shows a corresponding product example, in which the magnet volume and the arrangement can be used to draw conclusions about the magnet material, at least on the basis of the rotor, making optical sorting possible.

Figure 4: PM rotors from compressors equipped with hard ferrite (A) and NdFeB magnets (B)

A further increase of the neodymium share in the waste stream can be realized by additional pre-processing steps. For example, a typical electric traction drive unit weighing 80 – 120 kg contains 1.0 – 3.0 kg of NdFeB magnets, while the rotor, which is made entirely of ferromagnetic material, weighs 20 – 30 kg [7, 32]. Hard disk drives (HDD), which typically weigh between 100 and 500 g, contain approx. 3 – 20 g of NdFeB magnets [56, 57]. Consequently, a prior partial dismantling of relevant EOL products significantly increases the output and the energy efficiency of a possible sorting process. Unlike approaches based entirely on disassembly, this pre-processing can be very crude, as damage that could hinder the extraction of the magnets can be accepted. Corresponding application examples are visualized in the following Figure 5.

Figure 5: Potential pre-processing of automotive traction drives by destructive dismantling with hydraulic press (A) and of HDDs by shearing off the relevant section (B)

After pre-sorting and potential pre-treatment, conventional shredding can be carried out, usually using hammer mills. The shredding process parameters, such as the dwell time in the process chamber, must be selected in such a way that the magnets are not crushed too much, as the creation of magnetic dust leads to additional material losses due to magnetic adhesion [56–58]. Subsequently, conventional magnetic separation can be applied to isolate the ferrous fraction from the resulting granulate. Established technical solutions are overhead suspension or drum magnetic separators, which remove the soft and hard magnetic particles that are often sticking together.

Before further sorting of the ferrous fraction, a demagnetization step must first be carried out in order to dissolve the agglomerations and remove adhesions of the magnets to ferromagnetic objects. The following Figure 6 shows the typical clumping of still magnetized material that impedes sorting.

Figure 6: Typical agglomerations at shredded hard disks (A) and electric motors (B)

In general, two alternatives are available for demagnetization: magnetic degaussing based on alternating magnetic fields or thermal demagnetization. Only the latter is an option for shredded material. In this process, the material is exposed to temperatures above the maximum operating temperature, which leads to an irreversible loss of magnetization. Above the specific Curie temperature thermal oscillations completely

compensate for the dipole coupling forces causing full demagnetization [59]. For the basic Nd₂Fe₁₄B phase the Curie temperature is 312 °C although this value can be increased by the content of HREE. This leads to a required target temperature of approx. 350°, which can be technically realized in various ways and must be applied for a sufficient period of time [60–63]. For processing large quantities of material in a continuous process, electric or gas-powered continuous ovens are the industrial standard. The material should be distributed over a flat area in order to achieve homogeneous heating. As no short-loop recycling is planned, oxidation effects are not relevant, meaning that inert gas atmospheres are not necessary.

In parallel, the heating of the material can also support the following sorting process. When the Curie temperature is exceeded, the magnetic behavior of a ferromagnetic object approaches paramagnetic behavior. At temperatures above the specific Curie temperature, the parameter relevant for the behavior in an external magnetic field, the magnetic susceptibility, decreases increasingly as shown in the following Figure 7. This correlation is described by the Curie-Weiss law according to formula 1 [64].

Figure 7: Temperature dependence of the magnetic susceptibility of a ferromagnetic material (based on [64])

As the susceptibility is the decisive material parameter for the attraction force acting on a magnetizable object in a magnetic field, the behavior of particles during magnetic separation can also be directly influenced by heating them up. Even below the individual Curie temperature, hard magnetic materials have a significantly lower permeability respectively susceptibility compared to the relevant soft magnetic materials. Since NdFeB has the lowest Curie temperature compared to all other materials present in the ferrous fraction (cf. Table 1), repeating magnetic sorting of the material still heated above the Curie temperature of NdFeB leads to an increased deposition of material fractions with higher Curie temperatures. Consequently, the soft magnetic content can be reduced and materials such as hard ferrites, AlNiCo, or SmCo can also be removed to a certain extent, as they are still ferromagnetic and also adhere to soft magnetic objects. In addition, the temperature also prevents renewed magnetization of the NdFeB fragments. This approach is intended to be used to further increase the NdFeB concentration in the material stream, but experimental proof of concept is still pending. The implementation is planned with a magnet separator in combination with a heating and holding section. In any case, the parameters of this magnetic separation step must be chosen so conservatively that no relevant amounts of NdFeB are removed.

In addition to the low temperature stability of the magnetization, the brittle fracture behavior of NdFeB is a characteristic feature of this material family. This property can also be exploited by crushing the remaining material using a second hammer mill. Due to their high brittleness, RE magnets break down into much smaller particle sizes than the ductile soft magnetic components. Consequently, subsequent screening results

in granulates with a high neodymium concentration [62, 65]. An investigation by Peelman, et. al. based on shredded HDDs has shown a three- to four-fold increase in the RE concentration in the fine fraction [65]. Own qualitative studies using shredded HDDs confirm the significant increase in concentration of Neodymium. In particular, the fine fraction with a particle size of less than 250 μm contained almost a dominant proportion of NdFeB as visualized in Figure 8. This process step can also be easily upscaled using industrially proven tools like hammer mills and vibration screens.

Figure 8: Homogeneous composition of the fine fraction of shredded HDDs after two-stage shredding and screening

After the rough sorting, further sorting steps must be applied to remove contaminations for a sufficient level of purity for further chemical processing. In this context, the homogeneous grain size distribution favors fine sorting in the magnetic field, so that the significantly higher susceptibility of soft magnetic materials can be used as a sorting criterion. To do so, differences in terms of magnetic susceptibility can be exploited by creating different trajectories through inhomogeneous magnetic fields. One possibility is the free fall of the input material with a deflection by a magnetic field transverse to the direction of movement. The acting magnetic force on magnetizable particles in the magnetic field is described by following formula [66].

$$F_M = \frac{1}{2} V_P \mu_0 \frac{\kappa_S}{1 + E \kappa_S} \text{grad}(H^2) \quad (2)$$

with:

V_P	Volume of particle
μ_0	Vacuum permeability
κ_S	Volume-related susceptibility of the particle material
H	Field strength of the external magnetic field (including influence of inhomogeneities)

Accordingly, under idealized conditions and with homogeneous volume distribution, only the material-specific magnetic properties of the particles are decisive. Here too, experimental proof of feasibility is still pending. In particular, the interactions between the particles must be investigated. As hard ferrites have similar mechanical properties as RE magnets and in parallel exhibit similar permeability, an additional sorting step must be added to remove them if thermally assisted magnetic separation is not sufficient. In this context, electrostatic processes are considered that exploit the low conductivity and density of this ceramic material group.

4. Conclusion and outlook

Within the present paper the motivation, the challenges, and a potential approach for the recovery of RE magnets from shredded EOL products have been discussed. The authors' proposal is based on a multi-stage flow process that exploits the different material properties of the relevant material groups. Such a process chain must always be viewed holistically, with close interactions between the individual steps but also the upstream and downstream processes. The individual process steps are currently being examined based on tests with regard to their feasibility and suitability. If implemented successfully, the outlined process chain can close the current gap in the material recycling of RE magnets, which is essential for the economic strategy of most industrialized countries.

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